

Comprehensive Evaluation and Genetic Testing Confirming Chronic Neutrophilic Leukemia: A Case Report from INDIA

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Abstract

Background: Chronic Neutrophilic Leukemia (CNL) is a rare myeloproliferative neoplasm characterized by the proliferation of neutrophilic granulocytes. The most common molecular aberration observed in CNL patients is the somatic activating mutation in colony-stimulating factor 3 receptor gene (CSF3R), with the p.Thr618Ile (p.T618I) mutation being predominant and diagnostically crucial. Here, we report a case of CNL, with co-existence of mutations in CSF3RT618I and ASXL1.

Case Presentation: We present the case of a 62-year-old male patient with leukocytosis, anemia, and splenomegaly. Laboratory findings showed an elevated white blood cell count with a predominance of neutrophilic segmented cells, a decreased red blood cell count, and reduced hemoglobin levels. Peripheral blood smear and bone marrow examination revealed neutrophilic leukocytosis, myeloid hyperplasia with increased myelocytes, metamyelocytes, and neutrophils, and grade-2 fibrosis. A disease-defining mutation in the colony-stimulating factor 3 receptor gene (CSF3R) was detected, confirming the diagnosis of CNL. Co-occurring mutations in the ASXL1 gene were also identified. Imaging studies confirmed splenomegaly. The absence of the BCR-ABL1 fusion gene commonly associated with chronic myeloid leukemia further supported the diagnosis.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of comprehensive evaluation, including genetic testing, in confirming the diagnosis of CNL and differentiating it from other hematological disorders. Emerging evidences indicates that mutations in CSF3R (T618I) are early, pre-leukemic events, while truncation mutations in ASXL1 play a pivotal role in disease progression. This dynamic interplay between genetic alterations sheds light on the disease's pathogenesis, offering insights into potential therapeutic strategies and diagnostic criteria.

Keywords: Chronic neutrophilic leukemia (CNL), Leukocytosis, Myeloid hyperplasia, CSF3R mutation, ASXL1 co-occurring mutation

Introduction

Chronic neutrophilic leukemia (CNL) is a rare form of myeloproliferative neoplasm (MPN) characterized by the persistent increase in neutrophilic leukocytes, bone marrow myeloid hyperplasia, and hepato-splenomegaly. CNL is BCR-ABL1 negative MPN, since it does not involve the fusion gene commonly associated with chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) [1-2].

The first reported case of CNL was documented by Tuohy E.L in 1920. The patient was a 58-year-old married woman who presented with splenomegaly and persistent neutrophilic leukocytosis [3]. The patient eventually died as a result of the disease. Subsequently, Jackson et al. reported a case of neutrophilic leukemia characterized by anemia, splenomegaly, and leukocytosis consisting of mature polymorphonuclear leukocytes [4]. In 1964, Tanzier et al. further described CNL as a distinct entity [5].

The most common clinical manifestation observed upon diagnosis of CNL is hepatosplenomegaly. However, individuals with CNL can also experience a wide range of symptoms, including fatigue, weight loss, bruising, cerebral hemorrhage, and musculoskeletal pain. These symptoms may vary from person to person [2, 6].

Currently, there is no established standard of care for the management of CNL. The available treatment options aim to control myeloproliferation and alleviate symptoms, but they do not always provide a stable response. Cytoreductive drugs like hydroxyurea and interferon-alpha (IFN- α) have been used to manage CNL and induce remission in some cases. However, their effectiveness can vary, and they may not always lead to a sustained response [7]. Targeted therapies, such as imatinib and ruxolitinib, have been explored for CNL as well. However, these therapies have shown limited success in treating the disease [8]. Due to the potential transformation of CNL into acute myeloid leukemia (AML), which carries a poorer prognosis, allogeneic stem cell transplant (ASCT) is considered the best available option. ASCT involves replacing the patient's diseased bone marrow with healthy stem cells from a donor. However, the indication for ASCT in CNL is not well-established and lacks sufficient data to guide its use [2, 6].

The identification of activating mutations in the colony-stimulating factor 3 receptor (CSF3R), particularly the CSF3RT618I mutation, has been significant in the diagnosis of CNL [9]. These mutations are now recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) classification as precise diagnostic criteria for molecular testing in suspected cases of CNL [9].

In addition to CSF3R mutations, other genetic mutations have been associated with the progression of CNL. These include mutations in genes such as SET binding protein 1 (SETBP1), Serine/arginine-rich splicing factor 2 (SRSF2), U2 Small Nuclear RNA Auxiliary Factor 1

(U2AF1), Tet methylcytosine dioxygenase 2 (TET2), and additional sex combs like 1 (ASXL1). Certain mutations, particularly in ASXL1, have prognostic implications and can guide personalized therapeutic approaches in CNL patients [10].

Given the rarity of CNL, the uncertainty regarding optimal management and the potentially fatal course of the disease, continued reporting and investigation of specific therapeutic strategies and responses are essential. Here we report a case report of a 62-year-old male patient with CNL, contribute to the collective knowledge and understanding of this hematological disease.

Case Presentation

A 62 year old male patient exhibited leukocytosis, anemia, and splenomegaly. Laboratory results showed an elevated white blood cell count ($33.55 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$) with a predominance of neutrophilic segmented cells (89.4%), a decreased red blood cell count (2.66 mil/ μl), and reduced hemoglobin levels (8.9 g/dl). Peripheral blood smear examination revealed neutrophilic leukocytosis and anemia. Bone marrow examination demonstrated myeloid hyperplasia with increased myelocytes, metamyelocytes, and neutrophils, as well as grade-2 fibrosis indicative of myeloproliferative neoplasm (MPN).

The definitive diagnosis of CNL was established through the detection of a disease-defining mutation in the colony-stimulating factor 3 receptor gene (CSF3R), specifically a heterozygous T618I point mutation. Additionally, next-generation sequencing (NGS) revealed the co-occurrence of an additional pathogenic mutation in the ASXL1 gene (ASXL1 E635RfsTer15).

Confirmatory imaging studies, such as abdominal ultrasound and computed tomography (CT) scans, verified the presence of splenomegaly.

Taken together, the clinical, laboratory, and genetic findings strongly support the diagnosis of CNL in this patient. The presence of persistent leukocytosis, myeloid hyperplasia (increase in myelocytes, metamyelocytes, and neutrophils) in the bone marrow, hepato-splenomegaly are consistent with the diagnosis of CNL. Furthermore, the absence of the BCR-ABL1 fusion gene, which is commonly associated with CML, further supports the confirmation of the CNL

diagnosis. The identification of the disease-defining mutation in the CSF3R further strengthens the diagnosis, as this mutation is a key genetic abnormality observed in CNL. Overall, the combination of clinical, laboratory, genetic, and imaging findings, as described in the case of the 62-year-old male patient, provides strong evidence for the diagnosis of CNL and differentiates it from other similar hematological disorders.

Discussion

The clinical features of CNL are heterogeneous and often manifest as extreme hyperleukocytosis and hepato-splenomegaly. In addition to these physical manifestations, CNL can also cause a wide range of symptoms. These symptoms may include fatigue, restlessness, weight loss, night sweats, musculoskeletal pain, and hemorrhagic manifestations such as abnormal bleeding or bruising [2, 6].

The Maxson JE et al. identified a frequent mutation in the CSF3R gene found with the majority of CNL patients. The CSF3R gene encodes the receptor for colony-stimulating factor 3 (CSF3), also known as granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF). This receptor plays a crucial role in promoting the differentiation, proliferation, and survival of neutrophils. In CNL, activating mutations in the CSF3R gene, lead to the constitutive activation of the receptor and subsequent uncontrolled production of neutrophils. The most common mutation reported in CNL is CSF3R T618I. This mutation results in a substitution of the threonine (T) residue at position 618 with isoleucine (I) within the cytoplasmic domain of the receptor. This mutation leads to ligand-independent activation of the CSF3R signaling pathway, contributing to the development of CNL [9].

The discovery of CSF3R T618I mutation has significant implications for the diagnosis and understanding of CNL. The molecular genetics approach used by *Maxson JE et al.* has advanced our understanding of the molecular pathogenesis of CNL. It has shed light on the underlying mechanisms of the disease and helped to rationalize the use of pharmacological treatments. Overall, the incorporation of CSF3R mutational status into the diagnostic criteria for CNL has not only provided a diagnostic marker but has also contributed to a better understanding of the disease's molecular basis and paved the way for more targeted and effective therapeutic approaches [9].

In our patient, the presence of neutrophilic leukocytosis and the findings from the bone marrow aspirate and biopsy were indicative of CNL. The confirmation of the diagnosis was achieved through NGS, which identified the CSF3RT618I mutation in the CSF3R gene. This mutation is known to activate CSF3R, the receptor responsible for promoting neutrophil differentiation and proliferation, which explains the high numbers of neutrophils observed in our CNL patient [9].

Additionally, a co-occurring pathogenic mutation, ASXL1E635RfsTer15, was detected in our patient. ASXL1 is involved in the regulation of histone modification, and its presence in the context of CNL has been associated with a poor prognosis. This highlights the importance of considering co-occurring mutations as potential diagnostic markers for predicting the aggressive phenotype of CNL [10].

The identification of specific mutations through NGS and their correlation with clinical features helps in understanding the underlying molecular mechanisms and may guide treatment decisions and monitoring strategies. In addition, the co-occurring mutations in CNL patients can provide valuable insights into disease progression and prognosis.

The computed tomography (CT) imaging confirmed the presence of splenomegaly in our patient, which is consistent with previous findings reported by Szuber et al. The study by Szuber et al. demonstrated that CSF3RT618I mutations are associated with an older median age and are commonly observed in CNL patients with palpable splenomegaly [7].

By sharing clinical experiences and outcomes, researchers and clinicians can collaborate to develop more effective treatment approaches and improve the prognosis for CNL patients. It is through such efforts that advancements in the field can be made, leading to better management options and outcomes for individuals affected by CNL.

While these findings are intriguing, it is important to conduct long-term follow-up on patients in our study cohort to validate the role of co-occurring mutations, including CSF3RT618I, in predicting patient outcomes and response to therapy. Long-term observations will provide a

more comprehensive understanding of the significance of these mutations in CNL and their implications for patient management.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the recent diagnosis of CNL in our patient using the CSF36T618I mutation and the presence of persistent leukocytosis highlights the significance of this mutation in the diagnosis of CNL. This case report underscores the potential for targeted treatment strategies based on the specific phenotype associated with each individual's mutation. However, further research is warranted to determine the clinical utility of these findings in disease prediction and therapeutic decision-making. Rigorously designed clinical trials will be necessary to test the efficacy and applicability of targeted treatments based on specific mutations in CNL patients. These trials will provide valuable insights into the potential benefits of personalized approaches to therapy in CNL and contribute to advancing the field of precision medicine.

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Table 1: Overview of clinical, laboratory and genetic findings of the patient

Characteristics	
Disease	Chronic Neutrophilic Leukemia (CNL)
Age (Years)	64
Gender	Male
Hepatosplenomegaly (ultrasound)	Yes
Treatment	??
Laboratory findings	
Hb (g/dL)	8.9
RBC count (mil/ μ L)	2.66
MCV (fL)	106.4
WBC count (thou/ μ L)	$33.55 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$
Neutrophils %	33.55
Eosinophils %	0.3
Basophils %	0.1
Lymphocytes %	6.1
Monocytes%	4.1
Blasts %	0
Genetic and molecular findings	
NGS	CSF3RT618I; ASXL1E635RfsTer15